

Original Article

Contemplation of Political Transition in Chinua Achebe's Man of the People

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Abstract:

As disciplines literature and politics are intricate and multi-layered, literary works are products of political dynamism, and every writer has the effect of political environment in which he lives, in other words political environment shapes the personality, and thoughts of the novelist. Literary work reflects what is going on in a society, it may appear as an assessment of revolution, a procedure of freedom or it support a particular political ideology. The present chapter of the research paper focuses on the Contemplation of Political Transition in Achebe's Man of the people Achebe is politically committed writer, he has written about the effects of political instability and topsy-turvy political changes in post-independence Nigeria. He has brilliantly caught the essence of political flux of his country.

Keywords: *Contemplation, Transition, Flux, Topsy-turvy, Multi-layered, Pseudo-biological, Prevailed, Imperialism*

Introduction:

The relationship between politics and literature is the two-way relation. Achebe expresses a powerful cry for an end of the worldwide oppression; he is against the colonial imperialism. He labels himself as "a political writer",¹ he describes that his politics is concerned with universal human communication across the racial and cultural boundaries as a means of fostering respect. He is aware of the dehumanizing process of imperialism, so, he strongly raises his voice against the imperialism in his writing. His novels are extremely rich and incisive text of political analysis, he has always been conscious of the political character of his work. John Lindbreg states, "The relationship between literature and politics is multi-lane freeway traffic, following freely in both directions".² The African in English have depicted the political issues in his works; he has used novels as a platform to present the political scenario of pre-independence and post-independence period of their countries.

Achebe's *A Man of the People* basically deal with the political transition, it is an epitaph on the decline and fall of political norms, the basic objective of Achebe remains the same; cultural norms embody modes of perception which are intrinsic to emotional and moral experience. He has demonstrated the degrading situation in Nigerian politics, it gave scope to Achebe to remind the past values and ideals of society. He feels urgent need of the revival of the past in order to stitch the scattered roots of the Nigerian civilization. Achebe wants to revive remembering it once again in the modern Nigeria. The dancing and painting masked men were used their art to create spiritual awareness among the people, it had divine attachment, it was performed only on "some very special and outstanding events"³ are now invited them to welcome the politically corrupt leaders. Odili upon these comments: Here were silly, ignorant villagers, dancing themselves lame and waiting to blow off their gunpowder in honour of one of those who had started the country off down the slopes of inflation. I wished for miracle, for a voice thunder, to hush this ridiculous and tell the poor contemptible people one or two truths.⁴ Achebe views colonialism as the factor that had made the most devastating attack on the African personality.

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It was done in a systematic manner, and by consistently belittling the black people; the natives of Africa were criticized on the basis of pseudo- biological theorizing of the western people. Achebe's has primarily focused on the political issues created by the intrusion of the outsiders, his novels deal with the political struggle of Africans, his main concern is the consequences and the impact of the colonialism on the natives. His fictions distinctively mark his ability to create events, the mark of maturity lies in his ability to present successfully the political events at community level and at the level of individual acts.

A Man of the People explore the use and abuse of power by those who wield it, and absolute attack on both internal and external politics, the novel elucidates his statement. He says, "Europe conceded independence to us and we promptly began to misuse it, or rather those leaders to whom we entrusted the wielding of our new power and opportunity"⁵. He has depicted the conflict between different political centers, and the misuse of political power in modern Nigeria. The main characters are Chief Nanga, the minister of culture and the school master, Odili Samalu, through these two characters Achebe has shown the two opposite ends of the political spectrum, their relationship defines the basic problems of political morality. Odili has theoretical view of public morality derived from his western education; initially he is totally disillusioned with political affairs of his country. He rejects all local political allegiance; he condemns the corruption in the beginning. Nanga, the politician in power, occupies the other end of the political spectrum, he is a realist, he does not care for the political theories, and there is strange blending of fascination and reputation between these two characters. Achebe portrays Odili as a young as well as true political leader; he is contrast to the traditional corrupt political leaders like Mr. Nanga Achebe prefers to present the political corruption, and the central concern of the novel is the cynicism of both the politician and the people with regard to the electoral process. He is not satisfied with present political system in Nigeria; he wants to protest against the corrupt ways of politics, *A Man of the People* is prevailing his political protest, not only in Nigeria but all over the world, where the people are misused by the politicians. He writes:

A Man of the People, the protest is clearly more localized. I am talking about the politics of the country after independence. I am protesting against the way we are ordering our lives. The need for protesting will not end. I don't think, it's a question of protest against Europe or simple protest against local conditions. It is protest against the way we are handling human society in view of the possibilities for greatness and the better alternatives which the artist sees.⁶

In the novel, Odili and Chief M.A. Nanga are the main characters; they contest to be the man of the people, while an army coup changes the history of the nation, as an individual Odili and Max try to make difference without any popular support. Achebe examines the underline structural weakness of the new society which cannot stand the political changes; he renders the real aspect of modern politics. He begins the novel with satirical terms. He says: No one can deny that chief the Honourable M.A. Nanga, M.P. was the most approachable politician in the country whether you asked in the city or in his home village... they would tell you he was a man of the people.⁷

In this opening remark Odili, the narrator, shows that Nanga is central figure, and being the central figure, ironically, he is called the man of the people. He symbolizes a typical politician and also stands for the modern political leaders. He is popular among the people and he also has public contacts and many supporters. He speaks like a politician. As modern politician he is cunning, wicked, immoral, selfish and greedy. The politician like Nanga are the creation of the people in the modern societies, Achebe holds responsible to the public for corrupt and hypocritical politicians, Odili as the mouthpiece of the novelist remarks aptly, he says, "We all think we are first class people....perhaps it was their impatience with this kind of hypocrisy that made men like Nanga successful politicians..."⁸ Nanga is the minister of civilization as well as his speeches represent the community everything that a politician should do and be. He is deceptive politician because he does not practice his own preaching. The money that is supposed to go towards helping his community, he uses instead to build four-story building. The development of the career of Nanga as a politician clearly shows that Achebe focuses more on the political strategies of the leaders. He shows the switching of power between the old and new style of politicians and how the old-style bush politician, Mr. Nanga, is becoming more and more greedy as he learns the political system.

The politicians stand as the inter-mediating factors between the government and the common people, but Achebe portrayed their evil side. Mr. Nanga learns to be greedy as well as learns how to win elections through the corrupt system; the important thing for Mr. Nanga is that the people trust him. He relates to them more. This is because he considers himself closer to the common man and far away from the intellectual, who represents a more European style of living and thinking. By representing his country after colonialism, he has the incentive to stay as far away from the European style of living and thinking, and policies as possible to him. As Odili explains the story, however Mr. Nanga only tells the people what they want to hear about defending their way of thinking and Mr. Nanga acts in a voracious way to obtain what he wants in his personal life: money power and women. The narrator opines: Chief Nanga was a born Politician; he could get away with almost anything he said or did, and as long as men are swayed by their hearts and stomachs and not heir heads the Chief Nangas of this world will continue to get away with anything.⁹

Mr. Nanga is expert in using the dishonest techniques to lead the people by telling them one thing and doing another is what eventually brings his reign to an end. He taught Odili when was young and Odili also respected him

like as a teacher. He learns many things from Mr. Nanga, he becomes happy when he hears about the victory of Mr. Nanga in the first election, day by day Mr. Nanga becomes more powerful in the politics and Odili as reasonable man becomes more and more aware about the corrupt and dishonest politics.

While presenting dark reality of dishonest politician, Achebe highlights the quantity of burden imposed on the back of the Africans, after the departure of colonial power, the post-colonial political situation of Nigeria is the main concern. He shows that the leaders can reach at the peak of power that by dirty methods such as bribery, tribalism and deception. Achebe reveals that the sources of democratic system as presented in the novel is not compatible with the real democracy where the power comes from the people, through elections and constitutional intuitions. Achebe has demonstrated a point of view on upcoming democracies with the purpose, what really struck is that the system of democracy in Nigeria, which gives more power to the leaders and the common people are deprived. The leaders are servants in the real democracy but they have changed the course of system people are used as servants. They are used by the leaders like Mr. Nanga, and they are ready to wait for leaders in any condition. Odili's comments are realistic, he says, "Many villagers sat on the floor right up to the foot of the dais".¹⁰

Achebe also satirizes the young and educated politicians, Odili though represents good side of politics is also not ideal and clean he joins Max's political party for his selfish purpose and personal benefits. He wants to take revenge upon Mr. Nanga, He keeps hidden motive to get Edna from Mr. Nanga, his will be wife of Nanga, it is only because Mr. Nanga snatches Odili's girlfriend Elsie. Odili fights election not for public welfare but to defeat Mr. Nanga, It clearly shows that he is also not clean ideal and moral politician. He has slept with Elise when he was a student.

Max is better than Odili, but he has beloved and he also accepts money. He even advises to Odili to take money from Mr. Nanga. Achebe has projected almost all the leaders as immoral, and creates impression that politics is entirely corrupt and evil. The media, which is the voice of the people is also tactfully managed by the politicians like Mr. Nanga, after the visit of the editor of the *Daily Matchet*, Chief Nanga says, "If I don't give him something now, tomorrow he will go and write rubbish about me".¹¹ the freedom of press is also under the threat in the prevailed democracy of Nigeria. In fact it should be free but the politicians use it for their personal gain.

In modern Nigeria, the corruption is spread everywhere, the leaders and the policemen are also corruption the democratic system, and the public is also responsible for the corrupt system. They tell Max that the politician eats money, they also allow the people to eat, and people like the ex. Policeman discourage the good politician like Maxwell. The villager punishes Josiah for stealing the blind's man's stick, but they reward Mr. Nanga who is just a counter part of Josiah. These instances show that the novel elucidated Achebe's statement in which he says, "Europe conceded independence to us and we promptly began to misuse it, or rather those leaders to whom we entrusted the wielding of our new power and opportunity"¹² The behaviour of Igbo people reveals that the great ancient society begins to mislead by the political leaders.

People in Africa were able to check the corruption and oddities of a village, yet they were unable to understand with same values, the corrupt politicians at the national level. Prema Kumari Dheram has analysed the problem.

She writes:

Achebe's fourth novel *A Man of the People* is comment on the inadequacy of people knowledge and its inevitable consequences, problems arise as they fail to understand the concept of nation and national politics, so that values which stabilize and protect the village fail when it comes to save the nation from falling a prey to vested interest. A village has a collective consciousness and it can assert its will when necessary. However, people have not understood that the same value system has to function at the national level.¹³

Achebe's insistence on that will of the community strengthen in the national interest was very important, particularly at a time when greedy and shrewd politicians were polarizing the entire country on the basis of tribes to sustain their hegemony.

Chief Nanga decides to marry his parlour wife to uplift his glorious life in Bori. He returned to the native culture and tradition only to consolidate his position in the city. Thus, the conflict between the old and new values in African society was again deal with in the novel exhaustively; and this showed how the politicians were exploiting that crisis for their own selfish ends. They were completely insensitive to the needs and happiness of their people. Chief Nanga's desire to amass public money for his own comfort and pleasure is depicted throughout the novel in a comic manner, but below that apparent comedy laid the tragic atmosphere of oppressed and victimized people who, instead of feeling sad and angry, were happy, a young boy of Chief Nanga's constituency remarks:

Honourable Chief Nanga is my brother and he is what white man call V.I.P... Poor Innocent Victim... Look at the new house he is building. Four stores! ... It is my house you (Mrs. Nanga) have spoken the truth.¹⁴

Achebe wanted to show that when the leaders of the society looted the public money, the people acted like a buffoon, and wanted to have something from the minister. They were not educated enough about the functioning of the government that the minister was stealing the public fund while was their asset, their consciousness was alert enough to understand the fellow villager, but when it came to the national level they were ignorant, Josiah says, "What is my share in that? They are both (Odili and Chief Nanga) white man's people, and they know, what is what between

themselves what do we know".¹⁵ When they were told by Max about the corruption and malpractices of the leaders of the people's organization party, and the progressive Alliance Party and how they had risen from rags to riches by stealing public money, the people did not rise in revolt. The people simply surrender before the situation; both the political leaders and the men are equally responsible for the present situation of Nigeria. They do not understand the cunning Politics of their leaders. They fail to realize that their leaders deceive them by doing development, only when there is election. They do anything to win the election.

There are two basic reasons behind the political deprivation; first, the Self-centered opportunities like Nanga take full advantage of the people whose perspective of the nation's politics is dual. Secondly, in their view government and the working of the village affairs are two different entities. They do not understand the ways of the whiteman and so do not have the sense of involvement init. They find little difference in the situation even after independence; hence they do not regard themselves as part of a whole nation. Loyed Brown points out:

Nanga fails to be the 'man of the people' because the people do not exist at least, not on the level of that democratic nationhood which has been handed down the western colonialists. The 'nation' over which Nanga presides, is non-existent because most of the individuals within its bound do not perceive themselves as components of an organized national whole, but as members of specific communities described by the limits of village or tribe.¹⁶

The leaders do not think about educating the people, to understand the functioning of the democratic system. But they try to convince the public to behave irrationally for their personal political gain. These politicians are described as having a hold on everything, all the characters Odili, his father, Edna, her father and mother, Nanga, Mrs. Nanga, Josiah Elsie and the people are painfully aware of the political and economic impasse. They prefer to remain lethargic and cynically unconcerned.

The political leaders forget the welfare of the nation, they contest elections not to serve the nation, but to collect money and to revenge their rivals, Odili's fight against Chief Nanga is very challenging, as he is not involved in any malpractice while Chief Nanga is used all his shrewd, all cynical resource and the government machinery to drive his constituency to go for his support. Eustace Palmer sums up the entire political scenario of the post independent Nigeria. He writes:

In *A Man of the People* Achebe raised the curtain on his society to reveal the full honour of the status in most African countries' ministerial incompetence and corruption, social inequalities, rigged elections, thuggery, poverty, mass indifference, cynicism and intellectual bankruptcy.¹⁷

In such situation a good politician like Odili faces disillusionment and frustration because accepting bribe from one another party to stem down is common practice in democracy. Achebe has shown it in the case of Odili and Max.

Odili refuses to take bribe from his opponent Chief Nanga to step down for him in the election, but at the same time his friend Max took one thousand pound as a bribe from his political opponent Chief Koko for steeping down. Odili thinks that it has destroyed the moral force of their party. The political leader can go to any extent to come in the power, even they do not hesitate to kill one another, killing of Max by the thugs of Chief Koko is the example of brutal politics of Nigeria after independence.

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